

Servant Leadership and Employees' Motivation A Case Study of Public Education Department of Herat Province

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The current study aimed to investigate the relationship between servant leadership and employees' motivations. The relationship of the servant leadership dimensions - service, trust, humility, and altruism- were analyzed with employees' motivations at the public education department of Herat province. The researcher collected the data by standard questionnaire from 108 employees of the Herat public education department. The sample was selected based on a random sampling method. After applying the normality test, we used linear regression analysis. The research findings indicate that servant leadership has a positive correlation with employee motivation as the Pearson's correlation coefficient was 0.461 and the P-value was 0.000. Moreover, the correlation was significant for service, trust, and altruism dimensions of servant leadership. the correlation coefficients for each dimension were 0.403, 0.483, 0.493 with P-value 0.000 respectively. However, the hypothesis for humility dimensions of servant leadership and employees' motivations was not significant. The research findings show that the servant leadership style affects employees' motivations at the public education department of Herat province. Therefore, the decision-makers in the department should widely apply this leadership style in all aspects of the organization because employees with higher motivation may have better performance. As a result, the citizens' trust for public service in this sector will improve.

Keywords: SERVANT LEADERSHIP, MOTIVATION, PUBIC SECTOR, HERAT

Introduction

In today's organizations and competitive environment, leadership has a critical role in influencing, motivating, and obtaining organizational objectives (Bartlett and Ghoshal 2002). One style of leadership, recognized as servant leadership, emphasizes on service-oriented leaders. Servant leaders consider the assistances for their followers and the community at large (Sendjaya et al. 2008). In a paper under the title of the servant as leader Greenleaf ask a question, "Who is a servant leader"? He then defines the servant leader as a person who is a servant first. He wrote, "It begins with the natural feeling that one wants to serve, to serve first. Then conscious

choice brings one to aspire to lead” (Greenleaf,1977).

Patterson (2003) states that servant leaders guide the organization with emphases first on followers, whereas focusing on organizational concerns come after that or organizational concern is peripheral. Jennine (2007) believes that this style of leadership considers the philosophy of service. Servant leaders are the ones who serves the followers, satisfy their needs and develop and increase their capacity as the priority of all the work. These leaders, prefer mutual trust, empowerment, ethical use of power, cooperation spirit, and service value to followers to everything else in the organization. Prominent examples of servant leaders are Mahatma Gandhi, Nelson Mandela and Mother Teresa (Gary schwarz et al. 2016).

Researchers have considered different components for servant leadership. For example, Spears (1998) have mentioned 10 components and Patterson (2003) have highlighted seven components. In the current research, the researcher has used four elements of servant leadership which were identified by Dennis (2004).

Research Question

Does servant leadership style have relationship with employee’s motivations at public education department of Herat province?

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Servant leadership has relationship with employees’ motivations.

Hypothesis 2: Service dimension of servant leadership has relationship with employees’ motivations

Hypothesis 3: Humility dimension of servant leadership has relationship with employees’ motivations.

Hypothesis 4: Trust dimension of the servant leadership has relationship with employees’ motivations.

Hypothesis 5: Altruism dimension of servant leadership has relationship with employees’ motivations.

Literature review

Greenleaf has introduced the concept of servant leadership into an organizational context via his different topics. Namely, The Servant as Leader (1970), The Institution as Servant (1972a), and Trustees as Servants (1972b). Cerit (2009) indicated that servant leadership is accepted and practiced in various cultures; but its elements’ weights are different. Spears (1998) identified ten characteristics of servant leadership. Namely: listening, empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptualization, foresight, stewardship, commitment to the growth of people, and building community. Joseph and Winston (2005) found out that there is a correlation between servant leadership and leader trust and organizational trust. Ehrhart (2004) mentioned that Procedural justice is positively associated with servant leadership. A study by Gary Schwarz et al. (2016) found a correlation between servant leadership and job performance. Garber et al. (2009) indicated that servant leadership enhances collaboration. Jaramillo et al. (2009b) demonstrated that servant leadership improves follower’s wellbeing. Hanifah et al. (2014) found out that there is a significant relationship between leadership style and employees’ motivations and performance. Also, Sougui et al. (2017) stated that all leadership styles have a significant (positive or negative) effect on the employees' satisfaction, motivation, and performance. Khurram Zafar et al.

(2012) have found that servant leadership positively affects employees' motivations. According to Vadell and Ewing (2011), the Servant leader will increase the intrinsic motivation of the workers, in turn, it will boost the achievement of employees given that the person has a high ability to choose and high intrinsic motivation (Pardey,2007). Bass (2000) mentioned that leaders who use transformational leadership style effectively motivate their followers, and Storseth (2004) proposed that a leadership style including a "people-orientation" was recognized as a key predictor for work motivation. Ji and Yoon (2021) considered servant leadership as a variable that persuades intrinsic motivation and induces creative behavior. Gopal and Chowdhury (2014) researched "leadership styles and employee motivation" they stated that dissimilar leadership style factors will have different effects on employee motivations components.

Conceptual model

The conceptual framework for this research includes two variables. Independent variable or servant leadership is characterized by service, humility, trust, and love. Dependent variable or motivation is characterized by effort, performance, and result. Dennis (2004) identified the components of the independent variables and Rezaei Manesh and Sadeighi (2016) used these components, and also Victor Vroom highlighted the components of the dependent variable. The conceptual framework is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Research conceptual model (source: constructed by the researcher)

Service

Servant leaders provide the resources needed by others for their success. Service is an important characteristic of servant leadership and it has known as the hallmark of servant leaders (Covey, 2002). Servant leadership starts as soon as a leader accepts the position of servant. Service is the main part of the servant leadership model. Servant leaders are first and foremost servants at heart and are called to a life of service. Servant leaders lead based on the interest of others, and it may conflict with self-interest (Patterson, 2003). According to Amy (2012), Greenleaf considered substantial weight to servant leadership that takes the responsibility of thinking primarily about being of service to people. Patterson (2003) stated that servant leaders cultivating an organizational culture of service which inspires and motivates followers through their behavior.

Humility

means that one does not see himself superior or less than others. [Winston \(2002\)](#) states that humility describes the fact that a single individual may not understand everything and a considerable scope exists for input from others. [Dennis and Bocarnea \(2005\)](#) confirm that good leadership respect their followers and recognize their input to the organization so, they apply humility in this way.

Trust

Leaders build trust if they do what they say. [van Dierendonck, \(2011\)](#) considers trust as an important factor that affects organizational outcomes as it is a component of the significant mediating processes for servant leadership. [Greenleaf \(1977\)](#) mentioned that servant-leaders consider the opinion of followers while leading the organization. [Agarwal and Shankar \(2003\)](#) stated that a person's behavior is fundamentally determined by his morals and is more prominent than his personality. Problematic behaviors such as humiliation and exploitation can also be alleviated by changing one's undesirable behavior, greed and selfishness.

Altruism

[Kirkman & Porter \(2014\)](#) has concluded that altruism involves the principle or function of self-sacrifice and concern for the welfare of others. For instance, they have reported from [Mauss \(1990\)](#) that according to anthropology altruism concept means self-sacrifice While in social evolution research as [Nowak, \(2006\)](#) mentions altruism refers to the behavior of a person that rises the fitness or utility of another person whereas reducing the fitness of the performer.

Motivation

What makes a person move is called motivation, like fear, power, or love [Martin \(1998\)](#). The concept of motivation is based on this assumption that human behavior has its cause and for doing any actions, of course, there are motives ([Faizi et al. 2012](#)). Motivation is a process that begins with biological or psychological needs, it begins and activates purposeful motivational behavior in the direction of external stimulus [Luthanz, \(2005\)](#). Or “Motivation is defined as a set of energy forces that originates both within and outside an employee, initiates work-related effort, and determines its direction, intensity, and persistence ([Sougui et al., 2016](#))”.

Materials and methods

In this research, servant leadership is an independent variable and motivation is the dependent variable. The research could be considered as applied research. In the present study, the relationship between variables is analyzed based on the purpose of the research. For this reason, we can name the research as descriptive-correlation research based on how the data was collected. For data collection, we used standard questionnaires. The population in this study includes all the employees of the education department of Herat city consisting of 146 people from rank 2 to 6 from which 106 people were selected based on a random sampling method.

Data collection tools

For obtaining the research data the researcher has used two questionnaires. The first one was a standard questionnaire for servant leadership which included 4 components and 20 items. This questionnaire was

developed by Spears (2004). The alpha Cronbach for this scale was 0.943 which shows high data reliability. The second questionnaire which was about motivation included 3 components and 16 items. Each question had a multi-item scale from 1 to 5 (1= strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree), which were validated by earlier studies. The Cronbach's alpha for this scale was 0.871.

Research Findings

For testing, the research hypothesis and investigating the effects and relationships of the variables the researcher has used linear regression and Pearson's correlation via SPSS.

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha

Variable Name	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Service	5	.804
Humility	4	.749
Trust	8	.896
Altruism	3	.717
Motivation	16	.871

The above table shows that internal consistency for data of service, trust, and motivation is good since it is higher than 0.8, and reliability for data of humility and altruism is acceptable since it is higher than 0.7.

Table: 2 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	female	26	24.1	24.1
	Male	82	75.9	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0

The above table indicates that 24 percent of the respondents are females and about 76 percent are males. The total number of respondents were 108 people.

Table 3: Education of the respondents

Education degree	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
High School's Degree	21	19.4	19.4	19.4
Bachelor's Degrees	83	76.9	76.9	96.3
Master & Doctoral Degrees	4	3.7	3.7	100
Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Service	108	1.60	5.00	3.91	.79768
Humility	108	1.25	5.00	3.58	.85380
Trust	108	1.00	5.00	3.69	.82642
Altruism	108	1.00	5.00	3.77	.87809
Motivation	107	2.31	5.00	4.2	.58318
Valid N (listwise)	107				

Table 4 shows that the mean for motivation, which is the dependent variable is higher than the mean of each dimension of the independent variable. Mean of service, humility, trust, altruism, motivations are 3.91, 3.58, 3.69, 3.77 and 4.2 respectively.

Table 5: Correlation

		Service	Humility	Trust	Altruism	Motivation	servant leadership
Service	Pearson	1	.733**	.805**	.698**	.403**	.903**
	Correlation						
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	108	108	108	108	107	108
Humility	Pearson	.733**	1	.758**	.626**	.249**	.860**
	Correlation						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.010	.000
	N	108	108	108	108	107	108
Trust	Pearson	.805**	.758**	1	.795**	.483**	.960**
	Correlation						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	108	108	108	108	107	108
Altruism	Pearson	.698**	.626**	.795**	1	.493**	.847**
	Correlation						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	108	108	108	108	107	108
Motivation	Pearson	.403**	.249**	.483**	.493**	1	.461**
	Correlation						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.010	.000	.000		.000
	N	107	107	107	107	107	107
servant leadership	Pearson	.903**	.860**	.960**	.847**	.461**	1
	Correlation						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	108	108	108	108	107	108

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to table 5 all the above variables are positively associated with each other at level of ($p < 0.01$)

Hypothesis 1: Servant leadership has relationship with employees' motivation.

Correlations

		Motivation	servant leadership
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	1	.461**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
servant leadership	Pearson Correlation	.461**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	108

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to the above table servant leadership has positive correlation with employee's motivation in public education department of Herat province. The Pearson's correlation coefficient is 0.461 and P value is 0.000 which indicates that servant leadership is positively correlated with employee's motivation.

Hypothesis 2: Service dimension of servant leadership has relationship with employees' motivation

Correlations

		Service	Motivation
Service	Pearson Correlation	1	.403**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	108	107
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.403**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlations table indicates that the correlation coefficient equals 0.403 and P value is 0.000 which means there is a positive correlation between the service dimension of the servant leadership and employee motivation in the public education department of Herat province.

Hypothesis 3: Humility dimension of servant leadership has relationship with employees' motivation.

Correlations

		Humility	Motivation
Humility	Pearson Correlation	1	.249**

	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010
	N	108	107
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.249**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Contrary to other dimensions of servant leadership, analysis of Pearson’s correlation in the above table shows no significant correlation ($r= 0.249$ $p= 0.10$) between the humility dimension of servant leadership and employee’s motivation at Herat public education department. Because $p\text{-value} > 5\%$, there is insufficient evidence to accept the hypothesis that the humility dimension of servant leadership has relation with employees’ motivation at the education department of Herat province.

Hypothesis 4: Trust dimension of the servant leadership has relationship with employees’ motivation.

Correlations

		Trust	Motivation
Trust	Pearson Correlation	1	.483**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	108	107
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.483**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlations table indicates that the correlation coefficient equals 0.483 and P-value is 0.000 which means there is a positive correlation between the trust dimension of the servant leadership and employees’ motivation in the public education department of Herat province.

Hypothesis 5: Altruism dimension of servant leadership has relationship with employees’ motivation.

Correlations

		Altruism	Motivation
Altruism	Pearson Correlation	1	.493**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	108	107
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.493**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression Analysis

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.461 ^a	.213	.205	.51994

a. Predictors: (Constant), servant leadership

b. Dependent Variable: Motivation

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.664	1	7.664	28.350	.000 ^b
	Residual	28.386	105	.270		
	Total	36.050	106			

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

b. Predictors: (Constant), servant leadership

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.815	.258		10.896	.000
	servant leadership	.360	.068	.461	5.324	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

According to the above regression analysis, servant leadership has the standardized coefficient value of 0.461 and a P-value is 0.000. As p-value < 5%, we can claim that servant leadership affects employee's motivation at the public education department of Herat province. In the below tables the effects of each dimension of servant leadership on employee's motivation can be seen.

1. Service

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.403 ^a	.163	.155	.53617

a. Predictors: (Constant), Service

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.865	1	5.865	20.402	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.185	105	.287		
	Total	36.050	106			

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Service

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.984	.267		11.194	.000
	Service	.300	.066	.403	4.517	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

2. Humility

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.249 ^a	.062	.053	.56746

a. Predictors: (Constant), Humility

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.239	1	2.239	6.952	.010 ^b
	Residual	33.811	105	.322		
	Total	36.050	106			

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Humility

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.548	.240		14.779	.000
	Humility	.171	.065	.249	2.637	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

3. Trust

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.483 ^a	.233	.226	.51314

a. Predictors: (Constant), Trust

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.402	1	8.402	31.909	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.648	105	.263		
	Total	36.050	106			

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Trust

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.895	.230		12.571	.000
	Trust	.343	.061	.483	5.649	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

4. Altruism**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.493 ^a	.243	.236	.50969

a. Predictors: (Constant), Altruism

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.773	1	8.773	33.769	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.277	105	.260		
	Total	36.050	106			

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Altruism

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.924	.219		13.349	.000
	Altruism	.329	.057	.493	5.811	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Conclusion

In summary, the researcher has investigated the relationship between the independent variable, servant leadership, and the dependent variable, employees' motivation, at the public education department of Herat province. The research findings indicate that servant leadership has a positive correlation with servant leadership as the Pearson's correlation coefficient is 0.461 and the P-value is 0.000. Moreover, this correlation was significant for service, trust, and altruism dimensions of servant leadership with correlation coefficients of 0.403, 0.483, 0.493 with a P-value 0.000 respectively. However, the hypothesis for the relationship between humility dimensions of servant leadership and employees' motivation was rejected. The research findings show that the servant leadership style affects employees' motivation at the public education department of Herat province. Therefore, the decision-makers in the department should widely apply this leadership style in all the aspects of the organization because employees with higher motivation may have better performance and as a result, the citizens' trust will improve for public service in this sector as well as organizational performance.

References

1. Agarwal, A. and R. Shankar. 2003. On-line trust building in e-enabled supply chain. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 8(4), 324-334.
2. Bartlett, C. A., & Ghoshal, S. (2002). Building competitive advantage through people. *MIT Sloan management review*, 43(2), 34.
3. Bass, B. M. (2000). The future of leadership in learning organizations. *Journal of leadership studies*, 7(3), 18-40.
4. Cerit, Y. (2009). The effects of servant leadership behaviors of school principals on teachers' job satisfaction. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 37(5), 600-623.
5. Covey, S. (2002). Focus on leadership: Servant leadership for the 21st Century. *Servant leadership and community leadership in the twenty-first century*, 27-34.
6. Dennis, R. S. (2004). Servant leadership theory: Development of the servant leadership theory assessment instrument. A Dissertation presented in Partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree Doctor of Philosophy.
7. Dennis, R. S., Kinzler-Norheim, L., & Bocarnea, M. (2010). Servant leadership theory. In *Servant leadership* (pp. 169-179). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
8. Ehrhart, M. G. (2004). Leadership and procedural justice climate as antecedents of unit-level organizational citizenship behavior. *Personnel psychology*, 57(1), 61-94.
9. Faizi, Tahereh, Shahabi, Behnam & Gerami Poor, Masoud (2012), investigating motivational factors of lecturers at Payam - E- Noor University. *Public management quarterly* (Seventh year No. 24 PP 51-66)
10. Garber, J. S., Madigan, E. A., Click, E. R., & Fitzpatrick, J. J. (2009). Attitudes towards collaboration and servant leadership among nurses, physicians and residents. *Journal of interprofessional care*, 23(4), 331-340.
11. Gopal, R., & Chowdhury, R. G. (2014). Leadership styles and employee motivation: An empirical investigation in a leading oil company in India. *International journal of research in business management*, 2(5), 1-10.
12. Hanifah, H., Susanthi, N. I., & Setiawan, A. (2014). The Effect of Leadership Style on Motivation to Improve the Employee Performance. *Jurnal Manajemen Transportasi & Logistik*, 1(3), 221-226.
13. Hare, S. (1996). The paradox of moral humility. *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 33(2), 235-241.
14. Harwiki, W. (2013). Influence of servant leadership to motivation, organization culture, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), and employee's performance in outstanding cooperatives East Java Province, Indonesia. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 8(5), 50-58.

15. Jaramillo, F., Grisaffe, D. B., Chonko, L. B., & Roberts, J. A. (2009). Examining the impact of servant leadership on salesperson's turnover intention. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 29(4), 351-365.
16. Jennine, L. P. (2007). Investigation the distinction between transformational and servant leadership. A Dissertation presented in Partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree Doctor of Philosophy., Regent university.
17. Ji, Y., & Yoon, H. J. (2021). The Effect of Servant Leadership on Self-Efficacy and Innovative Behaviour: Verification of the Moderated Mediating Effect of Vocational Calling. *Administrative Sciences*, 11(2), 39.
18. Joseph, E. E. & Winston, E. B. (2005). A correlation of servant leadership, leader trust, and organizational trust, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 26(1), 6-22.
19. Khurram Zafar, A., Q. Ibn-E-Waleed, and A. Sadiya (2012), „The Effective Leadership Style In NGOs: Impact of Servant leadership Style on Employees“ work Performance and mediation effect of work motivation. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences* 1(11), 43–56.
20. Li, N., Kirkman, B. L., & Porter, C. O. (2014). Toward a model of work team altruism. *Academy of Management Review*, 39(4), 541-565.
21. Luthanz, F. (2005). *Organizational Behavior*. 10th edition, New York: McGraw-Hill Co.
22. Lyman, A., & Adler, H. (2011). *The trustworthy leader: Leveraging the power of trust to transform your organization*. John Wiley & Sons.
23. Martin, J. (1998). *Organization Behavior*, International Business Press, U. K, pp. 134- 135.
24. Northouse, P. G. (2004), *Leadership: Theory and practice*. Sage publications.
25. Pardey, D. (2007), *Introducing Leadership*. Taylor & Francis.
26. Patterson, K. A. (2003). *Servant leadership: A theoretical model*. Regent University.
27. Rezaei Manesh B. and Sadeighi R. (2016). Impact of servant leadership on employee's performance and motivation. *Public management quarterly*, Fourth year, No. 12, PP. 73-88
28. Rezaei Manesh B. and Sadeighi R. (2016). Impact of servant leadership on employee's performance and motivation. *Public management quarterly*, Seventh year No. 24. PP. 51-66
29. Schwarz, G., Newman, A., Cooper, B., & Eva, N. (2016). Servant leadership and follower job performance: The mediating effect of public service motivation. *Public Administration*, 94(4), 1025-1041.
30. Sendjaya, S., Sarros, J. C., & Santora, J. C. (2008). Defining and measuring servant leadership behaviour in organizations. *Journal of Management studies*, 45(2), 402-424.
31. Sougui AO, Bon AT, Mahamat M. A., & Hassan, H. M. H. (2017). The impact of leadership on employee motivation in malaysian telecommunication sector. *Galore International Journal of Applied Sciences & Humanities*. 1(1): 59-68.
32. Sougui, A. O., Bon, A. T., Mahamat, M. A., & Hassan, H. M. H. (2016). The impact of leadership on employee motivation in Malaysian telecommunication sector. *Galore International Journal of Applied Sciences and Humanities*, 1(1), 59-68.
33. Spears, L. (1996). Reflections on Robert K. Greenleaf and servant leadership". *Journal of Leadership & Organization Development*, 17 / 7, 33-35.
34. Spears, L. C., & Lawrence, M. (Eds.). (2002). *Focus on leadership: Servant-leadership for the twenty-first century*. John Wiley & Sons.
35. Storseth, F. (2004). Maintaining work motivation during organizational change. *International Journal of Human Resources Development and Management*, 4(3), 267-287.
36. van Dierendonck, D. (2011). Servant leadership: A review and synthesis. *Journal of Management*, 37(4), 1228–1261.
37. van Dierendonck, D., & Patterson, K. (2015). Compassionate love as a cornerstone of servant leadership: An integration of previous theorizing and research. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 128(1), 119–131.
38. Winston, B. E. (2002). *Be a Leader for God's Sake: From Values to Behaviors*: Regent University. School of Leadership Studies.
39. Winston, B. E. (2004). Servant leadership at Heritage Bible College: a single-case study. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*.

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